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4 **Sediment grain size and hydrodynamics in Mediterranean coastal**
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6 **lagoons: integrated classification of abiotic parameters**
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38 **Abstract**

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40 Integrated classification maps were produced by combining sediment grain-size and
41 hydrological data (water renewal time, WRT) from two Mediterranean lagoons, Lesina (LL)
42 and Varano (LV), Italy.
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44 The geophysical characteristics of the two basins, derived from detailed bathymetric charts,
45 are quite distinct: ~30% of LL (mean depth ~1 m) but only 3% of LV (mean depth ~3 m) is
46 shallower than 1 m.
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48 The sediments of both lagoons are mainly composed of mud (~80%). A detailed multivariate
49 analysis of grain-size data by EntropyMax classified the lagoon beds of LL and LV into five
50 sedimentary facies.
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52 WRT data, computed by a hydrodynamic model, indicated different hydrological conditions
53 in the two lagoons: LL showed a sharp west-east gradient, with a basin-wide average of ~190
54 days, whilst LV showed a fairly uniform distribution and a higher basin-wide average (~260
55 days).
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4 The distributions of sedimentary facies and water renewal times were combined in a
5 composite map representing the distribution of environmental patterns. The approach outlined
6 in this study can be used to improve zonation schemes by providing a hydro-morphological
7 perspective on transitional and coastal environments.
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12 **Index Terms.** Modelling, Hydrology, Geomorphology, Data analysis
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16 **Key words:** Sediment grain-size, water renewal time, bathymetry, abiotic classification,
17 EntropyMax, lagoon
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19 **Running Title:** Integrated classification of abiotic parameters in lagoons
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25 **1. Introduction**

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27 Hydrological or ecological data have been published for more than 50 coastal lagoons in the
28 Mediterranean basin (Pérez-Ruzafa *et al.* 2011). Comparison of these data makes it possible
29 to define the hydrological constraints on macrobenthic fauna (Barbone and Basset 2010) and
30 to evaluate the extent to which their ecological characteristics (e.g. fish assemblage
31 composition, zooplankton) depend on hydrographical or geomorphological features (Pérez-
32 Ruzafa *et al.* 2007a, Ferrarin *et al.* 2008).
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37 Maps representing purely abiotic environmental patterns have been widely used with the
38 assumption that biological trends can be inferred, although inferences are not always accurate
39 or justified (Levin 2001, Lucieer and Lucieer 2009). Creation of habitat maps entails
40 combining disparate data sets from biological, geophysical and oceanographic sources
41 (Brown *et al.* 2011). Pérez-Ruzafa *et al.* (2011) demonstrated that the variability of
42 Mediterranean lagoon assemblages depends mainly on lagoon size, the rate of exchange with
43 the open sea, differences in salinity with respect to the open sea, and the trophic status of the
44 water column. Trophic status may be forced by several environmental parameters including
45 grain-size, hydrodynamic conditions and the presence of organic matter (Lourido *et al.* 2010,
46 Malhadas *et al.* 2010). The approach based on the mapping of abiotic variables may provide
47 useful representations of environmental patterns, allowing scientists and managers to
48 understand the distribution of living and non-living resources on the sea bed (Stolt *et al.* 2011,
49 Anderson *et al.* 2008, Cogan *et al.* 2009, Shumchenia and King 2010, Oakley *et al.* 2012).
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4 The aim of this paper is to combine detailed grain-size data with hydrodynamic parameters
5 (water renewal time, WRT) computed by means of a numerical approach in the Lagoons of
6 Lesina (LL) and Varano (LV). Water renewal time data add to the characteristics of the
7 lagoon bed a “third dimension”, based on overlying water conditions, which strongly
8 influences benthic ecosystems (Ribbe *et al.* 2008; Brown *et al.* 2011).
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11 The data were mapped and overlaid in order to produce, in tandem with bathymetric data, an
12 integrated abiotic map. The abiotic zonation created in this study is flexible and can be
13 adjusted to highlight areas where biological data may enable habitat prediction and a focus on
14 environmental quality.
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21 **2. Study sites**

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23 The Lagoons of Lesina and Varano are located by the southern Adriatic Sea on the south-east
24 coast of Italy (41° 88’N, 15° 45’E) within the Gargano National Park, a protected area and
25 tourist destination (Figure 1). The tide in the open sea off the lagoons has a typical range of
26 about 30 cm. Tidal range in the lagoons is a few cm, and the narrow connecting channels
27 allow only limited exchange between the lagoons and the coastal system (Specchiulli *et al.*
28 2010). Wind-induced currents seem to be sufficient to cause resuspension and distribution of
29 fine sediment particles within both basins (Crisciani 1994).
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32 Given their surface area (50-60 km²), the lagoons are representative of large Mediterranean
33 coastal lagoons (Tagliapietra and Volpi Ghirardini 2006, Basset *et al.* 2006, Pérez-Ruzafa
34 *et al.* 2011, Duck and Figueiredo da Silva 2012).
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37 The genesis of LL and LV is linked to littoral dynamics that led to the progressive growth of
38 spits composed of clasts and other sediments drifting from the Fortore and Biferno River
39 mouths located to the west. During the post-glacial age these spits developed into a ridge of
40 coastal dunes which closed off the bays on the landward side, forming the two lagoons. The
41 lagoonal system probably developed after the Holocene climatic *optimum*, when the
42 neotectonic phases were already concluded (De Pippo *et al.* 2001).
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51 *2.1 The Lagoon of Lesina (LL)*

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53 The surface area of LL is 51 km², the catchment area is ~400 km² and the mean depth is ~1
54 m. The geological history and the morphological characteristics of the coastal zone suggest
55 that the lagoon's development and evolution are linked to interactions between tecto-
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4 sedimentary, climatic and hydrodynamic factors during the late Pleistocene-Holocene (De
5 Pippo *et al.* 2001).

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7 The lagoon's shape and depth have undergone changes due to constant sediment filling. Thin
8 peat levels alternating with marine sandy-silty sediments suggest that marine and marshy
9 stages alternated during the lagoonal system's evolution. Exchange with the Adriatic Sea
10 occurs through two artificial channels, Acquarotta, located at the western end, and
11 Schiapparo, at the eastern end of the lagoon. Overall, the lagoon is very shallow, the depth
12 never exceeding 1.6 m. North-north-westerly winds are very frequent in this area, especially
13 during winter, increasing sea water input to the lagoon.

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15 There are strong seasonal variations in salinity (from 10 to 28 psu) (Roselli *et al.* 2009).
16 Furthermore, the western region of the lagoon generally exhibits higher salinity than the
17 eastern region. This is due to the fact that the lagoon receives fresh water from small
18 tributaries, mostly located in the eastern part of the basin, which drain the majority of the
19 surface and sub-surface water coming from the adjacent karstic promontory. Partially treated
20 waste water from the lagoon's catchment area is also discharged into the lagoon. The
21 economic value of LL derives mostly from commercial fishing and extensive aquaculture (De
22 Pippo *et al.* 2001).
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34 35 2.2 The Lagoon of Varano (LV)

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37 LV is the largest brackish basin in southern Italy (65 km²) and one of the largest brackish
38 systems in the western Mediterranean. The catchment area is ~300 km² and the mean depth is
39 ~3 m. Bosellini *et al.* (1999) argue that the depression that accommodates the Lagoon of
40 Varano was originally a Cretaceous submarine slide scar resulting from a large-scale platform
41 collapse. Sea water exchange between LV and the Adriatic Sea occurs by means of two
42 artificial channels, Foce Capoiale on the western side and Foce Varano on the eastern side of
43 the lagoon. LV does not have morphological features such as intertidal marshes, intertidal
44 mud flats, submerged mud flats and navigation channels. The maximum depth of the lagoon
45 (> 4 m) is in the central-southern region. Salinity is relatively constant, ranging from 23 to 29
46 psu (Caroppo 2000; Specchiulli *et al.* 2008). LV receives freshwater inputs rich in organic
47 content from urban and agricultural run-off, fish-farming and livestock breeding (Spagnoli *et*
48 *al.* 2002). Other freshwater inputs come from groundwater springs in the south-western sector
49 of the lagoon and urban wastewater discharge in the south-eastern zone. Mussel cultivation
50 (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) is the most important economic activity carried out in the lagoon.
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3. Material and methods

3.1 Bathymetric datasets

The data for LL and LV were collected during two survey campaigns in May-June 2001. A total of 280 km of acquisition profiles in LL and 200 km in LV were recorded. A PSA900 vertical incidence echo-sounder manufactured by Datasonics was used for the channels (depth ~3 m), and a single-beam echo-sounder (Datasonics PSA-916, 200 kHz) was used for shallow waters (30 cm < depth < 3 m). The depth soundings were positioned with an accuracy of ± 1 m using a Fugro 3200LR12 DGPS receiver. To increase the coverage obtained by each track, 3-4 echo-sounders were mounted on a bar. The echosounder and the GPS antenna were mounted on a flat-keel boat equipped with the instruments used during the survey. Where depth was < 30 cm (areas near the shoreline), data were collected by the traditional topographic method (stadia rods with GPS). The survey was performed on a grid with profiles at a distance of 100 m. Tidal excursion in the lagoon was assumed to be zero (CoNISMa-DiSGAM 2002a,b). The projection datum is Roma 40 (Gauss-Boaga/East). The bathymetric data were interpolated and classified and are presented in the form of colour-shaded maps (Figure 1).

3.2 Sediment sampling and analysis (ternary methods)

Three hundred samples in each lagoon were selected from sites sampled by CoNISMa-DiSGAM (2002a,b). Sampling locations were distributed uniformly throughout both lagoons: the distance between samples was ~ 400 m. Sediment samples (~10 cm depth) were collected using a Van Veen grab. The samples were pre-treated with H_2O_2 (20 vol.%) to eliminate organic material, washed with bi-distilled water to eliminate chlorides and then oven-dried at 40 °C for 12 h. The samples were sieved for the < 1 mm fraction in order to eliminate clam shells and fragments. Grain size analyses of the sediments were performed by sedimentation balance using a SediGraph 5100 (Micromeritics™) particle analyser for the sand (> 63 μm) and mud (< 63 μm) fractions. The mud samples were pre-treated with 6% Na-hexametaphosphate solution for 24 h. Sediments were classified using a ternary diagram based on sand/silt/clay ratios (Flemming 2000) (Figure 2).

3.3 EntropyMax analysis

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4 The grain-size fractions were subjected to EntropyMax analysis. The concept of entropy, in
5 terms of particle size, can be demonstrated by considering a completely flat size distribution,
6 where all particle mass occurs with the same frequency throughout the distribution. This is
7 essentially a random distribution of matter throughout the size distribution, so that a size
8 spectrum with this shape has maximum entropy. On the other hand, in a size distribution
9 where all particle mass is found in only one interval there is no randomness of distribution
10 and the entropy is at a minimum. EntropyMax (Stewart *et al.* 2009) is a Windows-based,
11 Visual Basic 6 software tool that represents an updated and improved version of Entropy
12 (Woolfe and Michibayashi 1995). The software is designed to ensure optimal grouping,
13 maximising the inequality between groups of samples and minimising the inequality within
14 the groups, so that the distributions in each group all have similar shapes, and the shapes of
15 the distributions differ mainly between groups (Stewart *et al.* 2009). EntropyMax allows
16 optimal classification of samples into self-similar groups (Figures 3 and 4). The procedure
17 optimises the classification of N samples into R groups by maximising inter-group and
18 minimising intra-group entropy. The efficiency of this classification in terms of maximising
19 inter-group inequality is given by the so-called R_s statistic, which is the percentage of the
20 “data-set” explained, while the optimum number of groups is indicated by the Chalinski-
21 Harabasz (C-H) criterion (Stewart *et al.* 2009) (Table 1).
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37 *3.4 Hydrological parameters and description of the model*

38 In this study we applied a two-dimensional finite element shallow water model in order to
39 describe the temporal and spatial variation of the hydrodynamic regimes of the two lagoons.
40 The hydrodynamic model used in this study (SHYFEM, <https://www.ismar.cnr.it/shyfem>) has
41 already been applied to LL (Ferrarin *et al.* 2013b) and many coastal environments (Umgiesser
42 *et al.* 2004; Ferrarin and Umgiesser 2005; Ferrarin *et al.* 2010; De Pascalis *et al.* 2012;
43 Ferrarin *et al.* 2013a). For each basin, the numerical computation was carried out on a spatial
44 domain representing the lagoon itself and a part of the Adriatic Sea shelf in front of it (Figure
45 5). The finite element method allows for strict reproduction of the system’s morphology and
46 bathymetry. In addition, it is able to represent zones where hydrodynamic activity is greater,
47 such as connecting channels. The numerical resolution of the finite element model is
48 generally higher than the grab sample mesh, in order to ensure that each triangular element
49 contains no more than one grab sampling point.
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4 Water Renewal time is a fundamental parameter for understanding chemical and ecological
5 dynamics in lagoon environments and is also relevant to the supply of oxygen and the
6 removal of pollution (Andrejev *et al.* 2004, Stamou *et al.* 2007). In this study, the local water
7 renewal time (WRT) was computed by simulating the transport and diffusion of a
8 conservative Eulerian tracer released uniformly throughout the entire lagoon with a
9 concentration of 1, while a concentration of zero was imposed on the seaward and freshwater
10 boundaries. To simulate these processes in the Lesina and Varano lagoons the model solves
11 the well known advection-diffusion equation, which, in 2D vertically integrated form, is given
12 as:
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$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial uC}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial vC}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(K_H \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(K_H \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) \quad (1)$$

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20 where C is the depth-integrated concentration of a passive tracer, u and v are the barotropic
21 velocities and K_H is the horizontal eddy diffusivity coefficient, set at a constant value of 3.7
22 $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ (Cucco and Umgiesser, 2006). Fluxes through the bottom boundary are not considered
23 here. The transport and diffusion equation is solved with an explicit time-step scheme; the
24 advective part uses an upwind coefficient to ensure the exact conservation of mass.
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30 Through advection and diffusion, lagoon water mass is mixed with new fresh water and is
31 transported towards the open sea. The tracer mass in the system will thus decrease with time.
32 Here we also consider the return of tracer mass into the lagoon. The local WRT is considered
33 as the time required in each cell of the grid for the tracer concentration to fall to 0. More
34 details about the hydrodynamic model and water renewal time computation can be found in
35 Ferrarin *et al.* (2013a,b).
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41 The model was applied to the lagoons using real forcing data. The model was used to simulate
42 the evolution of a conservative tracer from June 2010 to August 2011 (May 2010 was used as
43 the start-up period). Open boundaries were treated with reference to water levels recorded in
44 Vieste (located at about 30 km from the eastern end of LV) on the seaward side and to the
45 fluxes of fresh water from the major tributaries indicated in Figure 5 on the landward side.
46 The numerical model has been already applied and validated for LL and the average
47 uncertainty in WRT, estimated by a sensitivity study, is about 10 % (Ferrarin *et al.* 2013b).
48 The application of the finite element model to LV is based on the same approach adopted for
49 LL.
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59 3.5 Spatial interpolation

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4 The bathymetric data have a 5 m cell resolution and the maps were produced using the
5 r.surf.contour algorithm (GRASS Development Team, 2013) with a contour step of 0.2 m.
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7 The WRT distribution maps were produced using the IDW interpolation algorithm (GRASS
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9 Development Team, 2013) included in the GRASS GIS software (Neteler *et al.* 2012). The
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11 main factor affecting the accuracy of IDW is the value of the power parameter (Isaaks and
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13 Srivastava 1989), which in our case was set at 2. Data points classified by EntropyMax were
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15 switched from discrete points to homogeneous areas following a three-step approach: firstly
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17 creating a Voronoi diagram from the points; secondly interpolating the EntropyMax classes;
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19 thirdly assigning to the Voronoi regions the mean interpolated value.

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21 The Voronoi diagram of a set of sites in the plane partitions the plane into regions called
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23 Voronoi regions, one to each site. The Voronoi region of a site s is the set of points in the
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25 plane for which s is the closest site (Fortune 1987). Using the v.voronoi algorithm (GRASS
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27 Development Team, 2013) a tessellation of the two lagoons was created to spatialize in a
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29 discrete way the "area of influence" of each sample.

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31 The data points were then interpolated by regularized spline with tension (Mitasova and Mitas
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33 1993) using the v.surf.rst algorithm (GRASS Development Team, 2013). Spline methods are
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35 based on the assumption that the approximation function should pass as closely as possible to
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37 the data points and at the same time should be as smooth as possible. These two requirements
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39 can be combined into a single condition of minimizing the sum of the deviations from the
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41 measured points and the smoothness seminorm of the function (Mitasova *at al.* 1995). Finally,
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43 each Voronoi region was assigned the mean value of the interpolated raster and reassigned to
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45 the closest EntropyMax class. The two layers (WRT and grain-size classes) were then
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47 combined to produce the integrated maps, using the GRASS r.cross algorithm (GRASS
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49 Development Team, 2013), which creates an output raster map layer representing all unique
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51 combinations of category values in the raster input layers.

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53 The bathymetric data were not used in the classification per se, rather they were applied post-
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55 hoc to the results of the two-part raster calculation to provide a mean value for each zone.
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57 Spatial analysis was performed and spatial maps were created using QGIS (QGIS
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59 Development Team, 2013).

54 55 56 **4. Results**

57 58 *4.1 Distribution of depths in the two lagoons*

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4 Colour-shaded bathymetric maps for the two lagoons are shown in Figure 1a, while the
5 distribution of specific depth categories is plotted in Figure 1b.
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7 In LL the lagoon bed and the hydrodynamic conditions have been modified by the dredging
8 of the two seaward channels and no intertidal marshes or intertidal mud flats are found.
9 Overall, the distribution of depths is quite uniform: the western part of LL is slightly deeper
10 than the rest, with depth values ranging between 1.2 and 1.6 m, whilst the eastern part has a
11 mean depth of 0.8-1.0 m. The deepest parts are two artificial channels, one south of the
12 Schiapparo inlet, and another in the central part of the lagoon, parallel to the southern edge.
13 They have mostly been filled in and the maximum depth is now ~ 1.8 m compared to an
14 original depth of 2-3 m. The inlets connecting LL to the sea are ~ 1.3 m deep.
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16 LV does not have morphological features such as intertidal marshes, intertidal mud flats,
17 submerged mud flats and navigation channels. The isobaths of LV are quite regular, following
18 the lagoon shore profile, with the maximum depth of the lagoon (>4 m) found in the central-
19 southern part (Figure 1a). The only exception to this general trend of the isobaths is a
20 shallower area in the NE part of the lagoon, adjacent to the littoral. The two channels
21 connecting LV to the sea (Varano and Capoiale) have a maximum depth of 4 and 5 m
22 respectively.
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24 To examine the morphology of LL and LV, the distribution of depths in terms of surface area
25 (channels excluded) was calculated for each lagoon (Figure 1b). A comparison of the two
26 curves highlights a clear difference between the two lagoons. A modal depth of 1-1.2 m is
27 evident in LL (Figure 1b) and a higher modal value of 3-4 m in LV (Figure 1b). The shallow
28 basin of LL is characterised by a flat bed with depths that lie mostly within a narrow range
29 (0.8 m to 1.6 m), with ~ 30% of the lagoon shallower than 1 m. The Varano basin is
30 characterised by a deep area in the range of 2.5 m to 4.0 m (~75%), with only ~3% shallower
31 than 1 m.
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33 *4.2 Comparison of the two lagoons: ternary results*

34 The sediments of LL and LV are mostly composed of mud (79% and 83% of dry weight
35 respectively). However, there are differences between the two lagoons with respect to the silt
36 and clay fractions (LL: mean silt 51%, mean clay 21%; LV: mean silt 66%, mean clay 17%).
37 The silt/clay ratio is therefore much lower in LL (mean 2.4) than in LV (mean 4.4).
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39 The ternary plot shows that most of the samples from LV are composed of coarser sediment
40 than the samples from LL (Figure 2), although the silt fraction dominates over other fractions
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4 in both lagoons. The different textural properties of the sediments in the two lagoons indicate
5 different hydrodynamic processes, and hence different depositional conditions, and different
6 terrestrial sources.
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9 Sediment composition is described by a diagonal band that gradually expands towards the
10 silt–clay axis. However, in LL the textural gradient shows a shift towards lower silt/clay
11 content. In LV, most of the sediments are richer in silt and sand. Most of the LL and LV
12 sediment samples are classified as slightly sandy mud and mud. A small number of samples
13 fall within the muddy sand category and a few are classified as slightly muddy sand or pure
14 sand (Figure 2).
15

16 In LL it can be seen that the sediments are dominated by slightly sandy mud, which covers
17 almost all of the lagoon bed. Sandy mud and mud dominate the western part of the lagoon.
18 In LV, muddy sand and sandy mud create a centripetal band that covers the entire lake bed
19 except for two areas, one at the southern edge and another in the eastern part, where slightly
20 sandy mud and mud dominate. The size distribution of the sediments follows the typical
21 lagoonal pattern: coarser sediments are found along the outer edges and finer ones towards the
22 centre.
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24 Given the generalised low sand and high mud content in the sedimentary environment of the
25 two lagoons, the data was subjected to further investigation by EntropyMax analysis.
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66 In order to better understand the role of bulk grain-size distributions rather than single grain-
67 size intervals we applied EntropyMax analysis to the LL and LV samples. As the number of
68 well-defined groups yielded by the software increases (starting from one), the C–H statistic
69 gradually increases until reaching a maximum value, after which it declines. For LL and LV,
70 using twenty-five intervals per sample, the C–H statistic peaked (indicating the best grouping
71 solution) at five groups, further division showing a trend of decreasing C–H values; this is
72 also the point at which *Rs* showed a reduced rate of change (Table 1).
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74 The five groups of distributions resulting from the entropy analysis are displayed in Figure 3,
75 together with maps showing their location in the lagoons (Figure 4). The groups are numbered
76 from 1 (pure sand) to 5 (pure mud) with increasing mud content. The sedimentary facies
77 corresponding to the five groups are as follows: (1) a clean, medium- to fine-grained sand (~
78 150 µm); (2) a bimodal muddy fine sand, containing a medium-grained sand mode (~ 200
79 µm) combined with subordinate amounts of mud; (3) a poorly sorted, medium- to coarse-
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4 grained sandy silt with a mode at $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ and a tail of fine clay; (4) a very poorly sorted
5 sandy mud, with sediments belonging to this group typically containing a primary mode at 4
6 μm and a secondary medium- to fine-grained sand mode; and (5) a sorted unimodal silty mud
7 ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$).
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10 In LL the finest sediments (group 4) are found in the western to central sections, while the
11 sandy silt (groups 2 and 3) accumulates mostly in the eastern and central areas. The coarser
12 sediments (group 1) accumulate along the northern shoreline. In LV finer sediments (group 5)
13 prevail in the central part. The sites located along the northern shoreline have the coarsest
14 composition (group 1). Muddy sand (group 2) accumulates all round the edge, while poorly
15 sorted sandy silt (group 3) is found in a band near the central part of the lagoon and to the SE.
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22 23 *4.4 Hydrological parameters*

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25 LV shows a fairly uniform pattern of water renewal times. The highest values (280 days) are
26 found in the central-southern part of the lagoon, while lower values characterize the area close
27 to the edge and near the connecting channels (bottom panel in Figure 6). LV has a basin-wide
28 average water renewal time of ~ 260 days. These are the first model-derived data to be
29 published for LV and are considerably lower than previously published flushing time
30 estimates, which ranged from 500 (Specchiulli *et al.* 2008) to 1000 days (Manini *et al.* 2002),
31 i.e. 2 to 4 times higher than our data. In contrast, as described in Ferrarin *et al.* (2013b), LL
32 shows a pronounced west-east WRT gradient, with a basin-wide average of ~ 190 days (top
33 panel in Figure 6), i.e., 2-3 times higher than previous data reported by Manini *et al.* (2002)
34 and Brugnano *et al.* (2011), who – on the basis of simple assumptions – estimated the average
35 flushing time of LL to be ~ 70 -100 days.
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45 46 *4.5. Classified map creation: EntropyMax and WRT*

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48 On the basis of the previously described detailed mapping of grain-size facies and WRT-
49 model results, it is possible to create integrated hydro-granulometric classes for the LL and
50 LV on a scale that is helpful for studying the various processes (Molinaroli *et al.* 2007;
51 Molinaroli *et al.* 2009a).
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54 Pearson's correlation analysis (2 tailed) of sediment facies at each of the 300 grab sampling
55 points showed significant correlation ($p < 0.001$) with both the WRT and depth values at the
56 same sample stations. For LL, sediment facies correlated more strongly with WRT ($r = 0.49$)
57 than with depth ($r = 0.20$), whilst the opposite trend was seen in LV (WRT, $r = 0.33$; depth, r
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4 = 0.60). In order to produce an integrated classification of abiotic parameters we first
5 spazialised the sedimentary facies of LL and LV, switching from discrete points to
6 homogeneous areas. We then integrated the WRT maps with these new EntropyMax areas
7 using the procedure described in paragraph 3.5 (Spatial interpolation). The limit values used
8 to classify the WRT maps for LL were 90 and 270 days (1st and 3rd percentile). For LV the
9 values used were 220 (this being the value that best identified the two areas influenced by the
10 seaward channels) and 255 days (1st percentile). The integration produced a splitting of facies
11 2, 3 and 4 in LL, and facies 2, 3 and 5 in LV, into two different classes each, making a total of
12 nine classes in all, with seven found in LL and seven in LV (Figure 7 and Table 2)
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21 4.5.1 Lagoon of Lesina

22 Class #1 is a medium- to fine-grained sand (150 μm) covering two small areas (~ 3% of the
23 lagoon) parallel to the northern coast, west of the eastern seaward inlet (Schiapparo), with
24 intermediate WRT values of 100-150 days and a mean depth of 0.6 m.
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27 Class #2 is a bimodal muddy fine sand, distributed all along the southern edge of the lagoon
28 and in a small area in the eastern part of LL. It covers ~ 30% of the lagoon and spans a wide
29 range of WRT values. Class 2 was subdivided into sub-class 2a, found in a band to the east,
30 between the Lauro river and Schiapparo inlet, with WRT < 100 day, and Class 2b, found in
31 patches along the southern edge of the lagoon (near the terrestrial inputs) and in a small area
32 behind the sand barrier, west of the Schiapparo inlet.
33

34 Class #3 is poorly sorted and bimodal, with ~ 20% sand, a mode at 20 μm and a tail of fine
35 clay. Class 3 sediments cover almost 40% of the lagoon and are concentrated in the central
36 and eastern parts, where WRT values vary widely. We therefore subdivided this class into two
37 sub-classes: 3a in the eastern part has low WRT values (<50 days), and a mean depth of 0.5
38 m. With an area of more than 6 km² (~ 12% of the lagoon) it is characterized by a wetland
39 with dense reed beds and clear ponds. Subclass 3b is mostly found in the central part of LL (~
40 25% of the lagoon), with intermediate to high WRT values (100-200 days) and a mean depth
41 of ~ 1 m.
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44 Class #4 is a poorly sorted mud with 10% sand. It covers ~ 33 % of the lagoon and is
45 concentrated on the western side, associated with high WRT values (>200 days) and – in part
46 – with relatively deeper waters. The integration of class 4 samples with WRT values
47 generated two subzones, one (class #4a) in the central-western part (~ 13% of the lagoon),
48 with WRT values of ~150-250 days and a mean depth of ~ 1 m, and another at the western
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4 end (class #4b, 20% of the total lagoon), characterized by the highest WRT values (>270
5 days) and corresponding to the deepest part of the lagoon (up to 1.6 m).

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7 The size of the different classes ranges from less than 2 km² for class 1 to ~12 km² for class
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9 3b.

10 11 12 4.5.2 Lagoon of Varano

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14 Four of the five sedimentary facies extracted by EntropyMax are present in LV, with facies #5
15 instead of LL facies #4 representing the finest end-member: the distribution of most of the
16 classes is somewhat concentric, from the shoreline to the middle of LV, following the
17 isobaths. The integration of EntropyMax results with WRT distribution produced the
18 following results:
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21 Class #1 is very similar to its counterpart in LL, a medium- to fine-grained sand (150 μm),
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23 and is found in two elongated areas parallel to the coastal barrier that separates Varano from
24 the Adriatic Sea. It covers a relatively small area (~ 10%) between the two seaward inlets,
25 Capoiale and Varano, with WRT values of 200-250 days and depths of 0.5 to 2.0 m.

26
27 Class #2 is a bimodal muddy fine sand, covering ~ 17% of the lagoon. The interpolation with
28 WRT determined two sub-classes, one (class 2a) distributed in two small areas (~ 3% of the
29 total) near the connections to the sea, with WRT values < 220 days, and another (class 2b)
30 occupying a 1km-wide belt all around the western and southern border of LV, with higher
31 WRT values.
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34 Class #3 represents a poorly sorted sediment, bimodal with ~ 20% sand, a mode at 20 μm and
35 a tail of fine clay. Class 3 sediments cover more than 30% of the lagoon around the central
36 part (which is also the deepest) and on the south-eastern side of the lagoon, where a broad
37 range of WRT and depth values are found. This was thus subdivided into two sub-classes: 3a
38 and 3b. Class # 3a (~ 6% of the lagoon) is found in the south-eastern part of LV, with
39 relatively short WRT values (less than 250 days) and a mean depth of ~ 2.5 m. On the other
40 hand, sediments belonging to class 3b (~ 25% of the lagoon) have slightly higher WRT values
41 (>250 days) and are deeper (2.5-3.5 m) than class 3a; they surround the deep central part of
42 LV on the south, west and north sides.
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45 Class #5 is a well sorted silty mud (mode 10 μm). It covers ~ 45% of the lagoon and
46 represents the most stable facies of the two studied lagoons. It is mainly associated with the
47 highest WRT values (>250 days) and is more than 3 m deep. The integration of class 5
48 samples with WRT values generated two subzones. Class 5a is a small area (~ 3% of the
49 lagoon) concentrated in the relatively more dynamic eastern side of LV with WRT values of
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4 200-250 days and a mean depth of ~ 2.5 m. Class 5b is found in the centre (~ 40% of the
5 lagoon), characterized by the highest WRT values (>250 days) and the greatest depths (>3.5
6 m).
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9 The size of the different classes ranges from ~2 km² for class 2a and 5a to more than 25 km²
10 for 5b.
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12 13 14 **5. Discussion**

15 *5.1. Bathymetry and grain size*

16 Bathymetric and grain size data have been already published by Specchiulli *et al.* (2010) for
17 LL and LV and Frontalini *et al.* (2013) for LV. The data were derived from ~15 samples in
18 both lagoons by Specchiulli and co-workers (2010) and ~ 50 sampling sites in LV by
19 Frontalini *et al.* (2013). The new bathymetric maps produced by this study used more than
20 250 km of acquisition profiles and the distribution and composition of the LL and LV bottom
21 sediments were analysed on the basis of grain-size data from 300 sites. The average
22 bathymetry was found to be slightly deeper than previously published data (Specchiulli *et al.*
23 2010) for LL (1.0 m vs. 0.8 m) and slightly shallower for LV (3.2 m vs. 4.0 m). The surficial
24 bottom sediments of LL and LV are heterogenous and mostly composed of mud (80%),
25 confirming the data of Specchiulli *et al.* (2010) for both LL and LV. Frontalini *et al.* (2013)
26 found much less mud (~ 50%) in LV compared to our survey, probably due to analytical
27 differences in sample treatment, which did not take account of flocculation, thus
28 overestimating the coarse fractions.
29

30 The relationships between bathymetry and sediment texture, as well as between
31 sedimentology and hydrology, have been already studied in the Lagoon of Venice (Molinaroli
32 *et al.* 2007; Molinaroli *et al.* 2009a) and Lagoon of Cabras (Molinaroli *et al.* 2009b). The
33 detailed bathymetric charts produced for LL and LV in the present study showed similarities
34 to sub-basin A of the Lagoon of Venice and to the Lagoon of Cabras, located near the Gulf of
35 Oristano, respectively. Indeed, LL is a shallow basin similar to the northernmost basin of the
36 Lagoon of Venice (sub-basin A: average water depth ~1 m) (Molinaroli *et al.* 2009a).
37 Considering just the shallow lagoonal flats of the latter, the two environments are quite
38 similar in both size (LL: 51 km²; sub-basin A: 64 km²) and sedimentary facies (clay/silt ratio:
39 0.5 in LL; 0.6 in sub-basin A). LV is rather similar to the Lagoon of Cabras, located near the
40 Gulf of Oristano (Molinaroli *et al.* 2009b). Both lagoons are characteristically bowl-shaped at
41 the centre; they have different surface areas (LV: 65 km² Lagoon of Cabras: 22 km²) but
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4 moderately similar depth (LV: average ~3 m; Lagoon of Cabras: average ~2 m). From a
5 sedimentological point of view both lagoons show high silt content (LV: 65%; Lagoon of
6 Cabras: 60%).
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9 In addition to the traditional textural classification, the ability of the EntropyMax analysis to
10 recognise discrete groups with similar granulometric properties made it possible to compare
11 and contrast the sedimentary facies of the two lagoons. Poorly sorted bimodal sediments
12 (groups 2 and 3) are frequent in both lagoons. In contrast, poorly sorted sandy mud (group 4)
13 was found only in LL, while sorted unimodal silty mud (group 5) was found only in LV.
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16 The characterisation of mud and sand facies highlighted by the EntropyMax analysis in the
17 sedimentary environment of the two lagoons may be useful for habitat suitability modelling.
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22 23 *5.2 Hydrological parameters*

24 In this study, the parameter used to describe the hydrological characteristics of the lagoons is
25 water renewal time (WRT). The average WRT values and spatial distributions reflect the
26 different hydrological conditions in the two lagoons. The water volume of LV is more than
27 four times that of LL (1.97 vs. $0.45 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m}^3$). Therefore, although sea-lagoon water exchange
28 in LV is three times that of LL (about 30 vs. $10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), the basin-wide average WRT of LV is
29 still higher than that of LL (260 vs 190 days). Freshwater inputs are considerable in LL (about
30 $4.5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, mostly concentrated in the eastern region) and influence the water renewal capacity
31 of the lagoon, creating a well-defined west-east WRT gradient (Ferrarin *et al.* 2013b). In
32 contrast, renewal capacity in LV is mainly controlled by sea-lagoon fluxes, while the scarce
33 freshwater inputs (less than $1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) do not significantly influence the spatial distribution of
34 WRT.
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37 Kjerfve (1986) sub-divided coastal lagoons into three geomorphic types according to water
38 exchange with the sea: leaky lagoons, restricted lagoons and choked lagoons. In accordance
39 with this classification, Roselli *et al.* (2013) recently classified LL and LV as “restricted
40 lagoons”. However, due to their long water renewal times and according to Ferrarin *et al.*
41 (2013c), they may merit an intermediate classification, between restricted and choked.
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44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 *5.3. Classified maps*

54 The relationships between hydrodynamic parameters and grain size in two contrasting
55 transitional environments, like the ones studied in the present paper (LL and LV) have already
56 been considered by Molinaroli and co-workers (2009a,b), who compared the Lagoons of
57 Venice and Cabras. Those authors found a good correlation between WRT and fine fractions
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4 (<8mm) classified following a traditional textural classification, but did not perform
5 EntropyMax analysis. As a further methodological improvement on Molinaroli *et al.*
6 (2009a,b) we integrated the WRT maps with the new EntropyMax sedimentary facies maps.
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8 The nine classes obtained, seven of which were observed in LL and seven in LV, were
9 spatially compared to macrobenthos and foraminiferal assemblages and zooplankton
10 distribution in the two lagoons as described by various authors.
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15 16 5.3.1 Lagoon of Lesina

17 Class #1 appears to be associated with marine sources. The highest zooplankton diversity
18 indices were found in this area, due to the co-occurrence of species of lagoon and marine
19 origin (Brugnano *et al.* 2011).
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22 Class #2 appears to be associated with proximal sources. Sub-class 2a is in the eastern zone,
23 in a belt 5 km wide where marine and terrestrial inputs (agricultural discharge) often mix
24 (mean WRT values < 100 days). The macrozoobenthic communities of this area were studied
25 by Specchiulli *et al.* (2010), who, in summer 2007, found it had the lowest number of
26 individuals and low species diversity. In the same area Marzano *et al.* (2003) found the
27 highest abundance and the lowest diversity values on an annual basis. Class 2b is distributed
28 in patches in the south-western part of the lagoon, where it is mainly associated with urban
29 inputs, and in the central part, where it is near inputs from canals and small rivers carrying
30 agricultural discharge. It is also present in a small area west of the Schiapparo inlet, behind
31 the sand barrier, where the possibility of inputs of seawater (and sediments) through five
32 buried ancient seaward channels was raised by Ferrarin and co-workers (2013a). Class #3
33 represents an intermediate sediment, mainly occurring along a gradient from relatively stable
34 to relatively unstable conditions. Sub-class 3a is associated with a wetland with dense reed
35 beds and clear pools and coincides with a Natural Reserve designated in 1981, an area of
36 animal repopulation of fundamental importance for many species of birds. Sub-class 3b is
37 mostly found in the central part of LL, which in the period 2000-2003 saw the formation of
38 thick mats of the macroalga *Valonia aegagropila* on the soft bottoms, affecting the structure
39 of zoobenthic communities; it was demonstrated that the presence of the alga was more
40 important than hydrological parameters in segregating this area from the rest of the lagoon
41 (Marzano *et al.* 2003). A few years later Specchiulli *et al.* (2010) did not find *Valonia* but
42 observed a decreasing west-east gradient of macrobenthic abundances. Despite the relatively
43 high WRT values, class 4a is characterised by high dynamics due to wind and currents and
44 often has medium-to-high numbers of individuals and high diversity indices for macrobenthic
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4 communities, with a prevalence of *Bivalvia* (Specchiulli *et al.* 2010). Class 4b is concentrated
5 in the most confined part of the lagoon, where high salinity values and progressive nutrient
6 enrichment over the last thirty years have led to a succession of uniform carpets of
7 macroalgae, from *Gracilaria sp.* to *Cladophora sp.* and *Valonia sp.*, which have occasionally
8 caused dystrophic crises (Manini *et al.* 2003; Roselli *et al.* 2009). This area is affected by
9 several human activities, i.e. aquaculture, livestock rearing and urban discharges. In this part
10 of LL Specchiulli and co-workers (2010) found that the high sediment organic load (TOC),
11 associated with the prevalent fine fraction, affected the structure of macrobenthic
12 communities, leading to decreased values for both abundance and diversity. This area can be
13 described as a “detritus trap” due to its ability to retain all organic C inputs, and was recently
14 chosen for bioremediation experiments (D’Errico *et al.* 2013)

15
16 This is probably the most vulnerable part of LL: in summer 2008, climatic conditions led to
17 the hydrological isolation of the western basin, producing a dystrophic crisis and a shift from
18 a macrophyte-based system to a phytoplankton-based system (Vignes *et al.* 2009).

29 30 5.3.2 Lagoon of Varano

31 Four of the five sedimentary facies extracted by EntropyMax are present in LV, with facies #5
32 instead of LL facies #4 representing the finest end-member.

33 Class #1 is very similar to its equivalent in LL, and appears to be associated with marine
34 sources. Specchiulli *et al.* (2010) showed that current dynamics are more active in the
35 northern-outer margins near the two channels and detected stressed sites along the northern
36 shoreline of LV with high sand content. Most of the fishing concessions, especially for the
37 harvesting of *Tapes philippinarum*, are found in this northern area, representing a further
38 source of disturbance.

39 Class #2 appears to be associated with proximal sources (terrestrial or marine). Two small
40 areas of sub-class 2a receive marine inputs as sandy sediments from the two channels, and the
41 more easterly one is probably also affected by a drainage pumping station. In these two areas
42 Frontalini and co-workers (2013) found a characteristic foraminiferal biotope, defined as an
43 Intermediate Marine Sub-biotope, with the highest abundance of *A. tepida*, *A. parkinsoniana*,
44 *A. beccarii* and *A. perlucida* and the greatest diversity. Near the western and southern shores
45 of the lagoon, sub-class 2b, a muddy fine sand, is mainly associated with freshwater inputs,
46 and in the southern part with input from livestock rearing and the town of Cagnano (Renzi *et*
47 *al.* 2012). Specchiulli and co-workers (2010) found high numbers of macrozoobenthic
48 individuals (2000-3000 ind. m⁻²) along the western shoreline.

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4 Class #3 sediments occur mainly along a gradient from relatively stable to relatively unstable
5 conditions. A small area with class 3a sediments is found to the North-east, near the mouth of
6 the Varano channel, and its instability is confirmed by the different foraminiferal assemblages
7 found by Frontalini *et al.* (2013) at stations within a short distance of each other. In the south-
8 eastern part of LV, which has sediment of both class 3a (near the shoreline) and 3b (deeper,
9 with higher WRT), Specchiulli and co-workers (2010) found the highest macrofaunal
10 diversity indices, associated with two wastewater drains rich in phosphorus. Frontalini *et al.*
11 (2013) found high diversity values for foraminiferal assemblages as well, and this group of
12 stations were defined as an Inner Marginal Lake Biotope. In the western part, with sediment
13 belonging to sub-class 3b, Belmonte *et al.* (2011) found freshwater species (*Daphnia sp.*,
14 *Calanipeda aquaedulcis*, Rotifera), probably due to its proximity to freshwater springs.

15
16 Class #5 represents the most stable facies of the two studied lagoons. A small area (< 2 km²)
17 near the eastern shore with lower water residence time belongs to class 5a. Belmonte *et al.*
18 (2011) found several organisms of marine origin on the eastern side of LV (sub-class 5a),
19 confirming the relatively high water dynamics. Again on the eastern side Specchiulli *et al.*
20 (2010) found high species richness with Polychaetes (*Perinereis cultrifera*) prevailing over
21 Bivalvia (*Loripes lacteus*). In contrast, the same authors found the lowest abundances and
22 diversity indices in the central part of LV (class 5b). Similar findings are reported by
23 Belmonte *et al.* (2011), who found broadly similar zooplankton community composition in
24 the eastern and central areas of LV, although the central area had the lowest abundances. He
25 found high densities of the jellyfish *Aurelia Aurita*, proposing that enclosed habitats
26 characterised by calm waters and high food availability enhanced the probability of jellyfish
27 survival. Specchiulli *et al.* (2010) found much lower abundance of *Musculista senhousia* in
28 sub-class 5b (central lagoon) than both the western and eastern sides of the lagoon, due to
29 summer hypoxia and anoxia. This result suggests that when coupled with low water exchange
30 and high temperatures in summer, organic matter decomposition processes promote more
31 rapid oxygen depletion in the central part of LV than in other areas (Specchiulli *et al.* 2010).
32 In this area Specchiulli *et al.* (2008) showed an increase in ammonia with temperature due to
33 remineralising processes.

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35 In summary, the nine classes obtained by integrating the five facies of the EntropyMax
36 analysis with the model-derived WRT values highlighted similarities and differences between
37 LL and LV. By comparing the classes with published data it is seen that class 1 is of marine
38 origin in both lagoons, with relatively low WRT values and relatively shallow depths. Class 1
39 in LV also deserves attention due to the increasing intensity of *Tapes philippinarum*

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4 harvesting. Class 2 indicated proximal terrestrial sources with some inputs from the sea. Class
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6 3 was clearly distributed along a west-east gradient in LL (following WRT values), class 3a
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8 coinciding with the Lesina Natural Reserve, of great ecological importance, and thus
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10 confirming the association of good environmental quality with strong hydrodynamics (the
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12 lowest WRT values, < 50 days). In spite of their sedimentological and hydrodynamic
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14 differences, Classes 2 and 3 in LV sustain biological communities with higher diversity and
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16 species richness than the central area of LV. Class 4b, on the western side of LL, and class 5b,
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18 in the centre of LV, were associated with the highest mud content and the highest WRT
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20 values, making them the most vulnerable to eutrophication effects, particularly the
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22 sedimentation of organic matter. A specific focus on the welfare of these areas may therefore
23
24 be advisable.

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26 The size of the different classes ranges from less than 2 km² for class 1 in LL and 5a in LV to
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28 more than 25 km² for 5b in LV: spatial scales that are comparable to the variation of benthic
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30 assemblages (macrophytes and fish), which were found to vary along the confinement
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32 gradient at a scale of 10⁰-10¹ km in Mar Menor (Perez-Ruzafa *et al.* 2007a).

33
34 Comparison of human impact across lagoons is hindered by high-scale variability of
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36 hydrographical and geomorphological features; as Perez Ruzafa *et al.* (2007b) suggested, one
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38 way of dealing with this is to establish a monitoring plan for each class found in LL and LV,
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40 with special attention to the more vulnerable areas.

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67 In semi-closed shallow coastal environments, like LL and LV, where local ecosystem
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69 conditions depend on the dynamics of the whole basin, areas with longer renewal times
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71 exhibit a higher degree of eutrophication and saprobity, defined as the state of the
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73 environment resulting from the input and decomposition of organic matter and the removal of
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75 its catabolites (Tagliapietra *et al.* 2012), than those with shorter times. Consequently, the
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77 spatial distribution of water renewal time, together with sediment characteristics, could help
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79 to explain the heterogeneous spatial distributions of benthic assemblages and trace elements
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81 found in the sediments of these lagoons. Indeed, an additional benefit of these models is that
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83 the resolution can be tailored to provide detailed information at points of interest, i.e. where
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85 grab samples are collected.

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87 With these maps, we explored the potential relationships between physical and biological
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89 parameters. In some cases, we discovered a clear match between abiotic classification and

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4 biota; in others, however, relationships were more difficult to discern and require further
5 investigation.
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7 Specifically the following points can be listed as main conclusions:
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- 10 1. New bathymetric charts of LL and LV were produced which described in detail the
11 geophysical characteristics of the two basins: the mean depth of LL is ~1 m (~30% is
12 shallower than 1 m) whilst the mean depth of LV is ~3 m (~3% is shallower than 1 m).
13
- 14 2. In LL and LV, five sediment facies were identified: (1) a clean, medium- to fine-grained
15 sand; (2) a bimodal muddy fine sand, containing a medium-grained sand mode combined
16 with subordinate amounts of mud; (3) a poorly sorted, medium- to coarse-grained sandy
17 silt; (4) a very poorly sorted sandy mud; and (5) a sorted unimodal silty mud. The poorly
18 sorted sandy mud (facies 4) was found only in LL and the sorted unimodal silty mud
19 (facies 5) only in LV.
20
- 21 3. LL is characterised by high variability of water renewal times (from ~2 to 291 days). In
22 LV water renewal times are more uniform (from 134 to ~281 days). The waters in the
23 eastern part of LL and the area near the shoreline of LV are replaced more rapidly than the
24 western and deeper parts of the two lagoons.
25
- 26 4. The combination of sedimentological (grain-size) and hydrological (water renewal time)
27 data produced an integrated classification of abiotic parameters that is useful for
28 identifying vulnerable areas already suffering from environmental problems. Indeed,
29 facies 4 and 5, characterized by WRT>250 and fine sediments, correspond to areas where
30 dystrophic events have been observed in both lagoons in recent years.
31
- 32 5. The importance (weight) of each abiotic parameter in the classification is different for the
33 two lagoons. Comparison with recent results (biotic and abiotic data) obtained in the two
34 lagoons shows that hydrodynamics is the forcing factor for zonation in LL, while
35 sediment properties play the main role in LV..
36
- 37 6. Although this study makes many simplifications, the integrated abiotic classification
38 should provide the coastal management community with new insight into the dynamics of
39 estuarine and transitional environments. The methods will be applicable to most large
40 Mediterranean coastal lagoons and to a variety of transitional and coastal environments.
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57 **Acknowledgments**

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Figure Captions

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6 Figure 1. Map of Lesina and Varano lagoons with bathymetric maps (a). Distribution of
7 specific elevation categories in Lagoons of Lesina (dotted line) and Varano (solid line)
8 (b). Projection datum is Roma 40 (Gauss-Boaga/East).
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10
11 Figure 2. Ternary diagram of surficial LL and LV sediments based on sand/silt/clay ratios.
12
13 Figure 3. Grain-size distribution groups (textural facies) in LL and LV derived from
14 EntropyMax: all distributions (above) and mean distributions (below).
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16 Figure 4. Areal distribution in LL and LV of sediment facies derived from EntropyMax.
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18 Figure 5. Computational finite element grids for Lesina and Varano lagoons.
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20 Figure 6. Distribution of water renewal time (days) in LL and LV.
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22 Figure 7. Composite map of integrated sediment classes in LL and LV. Numbers indicate
23 combinations and corresponding zones.
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Figure 1

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Figure 7

Table 1. Calinski–Harabasz (C–H) pseudo F-statistic and Rs values for 25-interval LL and LV size data; optimal grouping is attained at peak C–H and at point of reduced rate of change in Rs

Number of groups	C-H pseudo F-statistic	Rs-values
2	188.39	35
3	181.54	47
4	248.71	60
5	276.78	67
6	237.53	69
7	264.71	71
8	261.47	73
9	261.86	74
10	196.16	75

Table 2.doc

Table 2- Essential data for sediment classes identified in each lagoon (LL and LV). Numbers indicate corresponding areas in Figure 7. Second column shows percentage of lagoon area covered by each class.

LESINA

class	% Area	EntropyMax facies	source/input/condition
1	3	medium- to fine-grained sand (150 μ m)	marine input
2a	10	bimodal muddy fine sand (sand mode 200 μ m, mud)	terrestrial and marine sources
2b	18		proximal terrestrial sources
3a	12	poorly sorted, medium- to coarse-grained sandy silt (mode at 20 μ m, tail of fine clay)	stable/unstable conditions: strong dynamics
3b	24		stable/unstable conditions: weak dynamics
4a	13	poorly sorted sandy mud (fine mode at 4 μ m, medium- to fine-grained sand mode)	urban & aquaculture discharges: strong dynamics
4b	20		cattle farm & aquaculture discharges: confinement

VARANO

class	% Area	EntropyMax facies	source/input/condition
1	9	medium- to fine-grained sand (150 μ m)	marine input
2a	3	bimodal muddy fine sand (sand mode 200 μ m, mud)	terrestrial and marine sources
2b	14		proximal terrestrial sources
3a	6	poorly sorted, medium- to coarse-grained sandy silt (mode at 20 μ m, tail of fine clay)	stable/unstable conditions: strong dynamics
3b	25		stable/unstable conditions: freshwater springs
5a	3	sorted unimodal silty mud (mode at 10 μ m)	stable mud facies/slightly stronger dynamics \rightarrow coarser mode
5b	40		stable mud facies/stratification

Electronic Supplementary Material

[Click here to download Electronic Supplementary Material: Molinaroli et al. _ Dataset Lagoon of Lesina.xls](#)

Electronic Supplementary Material

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